

Studies on Polymerization of Safflower Oil in an Eutectic Saltbath. Part II

A. E. RHEINECK and S. N. KOLEY*

Polymers and Coatings Department, College of Chemistry and Physics, North Dakota State University,
Fargo, North Dakota

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In the present investigation, safflower oil was passed through an eutectic saltbath consisting of 54.5% KNO_3 and 45.5% NaNO_3 (m.p. 218°) at temperatures varying from 300° - 320° . In some cases 0.2% lead oleate (as lead) on oil weight was used as catalyst. The following are the new findings in this new type of bodied oil: (a) The bodied safflower oils of viscosities 0.84-2.4 stokes were obtained within a short time of contact; (b) the bodied oils are heterogeneous and separate into two layers on standing. The bodied mass were separated into two fractions using two volumes of dry acetone at room temperature and were analyzed. The free fatty acids were extracted and analyzed by GLC. Only the results of the analyses of the acetone soluble fractions are described in this paper. The methyl esters of the acetone soluble fractions were prepared and analyzed by GLC in DEGS and Apiezon-L columns. The esters were also distilled under vacuum and analyzed. The free fatty acids and the esters of acetone soluble fractions contain acids of variable and fractional carbon numbers. So it appears that a number of new fatty acids are produced by the contact of molten salts.

IN the previous paper, the studies were made on the bodying of linseed oil¹. In the previous investigation, attempts were made to study the bodying of an oil rich in dienolic acids and free from trienoic acids. The cyclic or chain nature of autoxidation reaction is well established. The reaction chain can be initiated by the attack of any free radical upon linoleate. The most probable radicals to initiate chains are those formed by decomposition of peroxide. Lundberg and Chipault² observed that highly purified ethyl linoleate had a long induction period i.e., it had no measurable oxidation rate for several hours after exposure to oxygen. According to Gibson³ the activation of molecules is considered to proceed by bond fission, each broken bond resulting in two centers of activity which may rearrange to form free radicals or new bonds. Components that may be activated are oxygen, methylene, tertiary carbon or unsaturated groups. The autoxidation is divided in two stages (i) the induction period, during which the initial formation of hydroperoxide from methyl linoleate takes place and (ii) the autoxidation proper, which is catalyzed by hydroperoxide stage, is a chain reaction cycle operating through H- and HOO- free radicals. The hydroperoxide decomposes more or less quickly and reaction occurs through either (a) an oxygen atom diradical, $\cdot\text{O}\cdot$, or (b) a hydroxyl radical, $\cdot\text{OH}$. A hydroperoxide group attacks methylene, tertiary carbon or unsaturated groups within its own or other molecules, which may thereby be split into two parts forming mono, di- and trimeric products. The chief decomposition products are considered to be unsaturated hydroxyl,

$\cdot\text{CH} : \text{CH} \cdot \text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot$; dihydroxyl $\cdot\text{CH}(\text{OH}) \cdot \text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot$ and carboxyl compounds, $\cdot\text{CO}$.

Allen, Jackson and Kummerow⁴ compared the oxidation of 9,12-linoleate and its conjugated isomer and found that in early stages of oxidation of 9,12-linoleate, all the oxygen adsorbed was found as peroxide whereas in the oxidation of the conjugated isomer no peroxide accumulated in the first stage of the reaction and oxidation rate is slower in case of conjugated isomer. The slower oxidation rate agrees with the findings of Zimmerman and Rheineck⁵. On the other hand, Holman and Elmer⁶ showed that there is no essential difference in the rates of oxidation of non-conjugated and conjugated linoleic acids. Kawada, Krishnamurthy, Mukherjee and Chang⁷ oxidized corn oil at 185° for 3 hr and thirty different acids were characterized. These consisted of keto, hydroxy, dicarboxylic and aromatic acids.

Artman and Alexander⁸ also identified aromatic acid in partially hydrogenated safflower oil when heated for 10, 18.5 hr days and 24 hr in air at 185° .

Experimental

In the present work alkali refined safflower oil, ARS, was passed through the molten eutectic salt mixture composed of 54.5% KNO_3 and 45.5% NaNO_3 . In some experiments 0.2% lead oleate as lead on oil weight was used as catalyst. The apparatus was previously¹ described. The oil was first preheated to 10° below the temperature of the saltbath and then passed through the bath at different temperatures and rates. The range was 314° to 320° and the rates varied from 1 to 25 ml/min. as given in Table I. The free fatty acids were extracted from

* Present address: Directorate of Industries, Industrial Research Laboratory, Canal South Road, Calcutta-15.

TABLE 1. BODIING CONDITION AND PROPERTIES OF THE OIL

Sample No.	Bodiyng Conditions			Properties of the Oils	
	Compn. of Saltbath (wt.%)	Temp. of Bath (°C)	Rate of Flow of Oil (ml/min)	Viscosity of the oil (stokes)	Acetone-Solubility (wt.%)
1	54.5% KNO ₃ and 45.5% NaNO ₃	314	2.5	0.66	—
2	"	320	25.0	0.66	—
3	"	320	12.0	0.85	90.5
4	"	320	1.0	1.21	88.3
5*	"	320	12.0	1.01	89.2
6*	"	320	4.0	2.29-2.56	79.8

* Bodied with 0.2% lead oleate as catalyst.

TABLE 2. COMPOSITION OF FREE FATTY ACIDS FROM BODIED SAFFLOWER OIL

Carbon number on DEGS	Carbon number on Apiezon-L	Tentative identification	SO	%Composition based on DEGS			
				3	4	5	6
10.0	10.0	C ₁₀ Saturated	—	tr	tr	tr	tr
11.0	11.0	C ₁₁ Saturated	—	tr	tr	tr	tr
11.7	—	—	—	tr	tr	tr	0.5
12.0	12.0	C ₁₂ Saturated	—	tr	tr	tr	0.4
13.4	12.5	—	—	tr	tr	tr	0.4
14.0	14.0	C ₁₄ Saturated	—	tr	tr	0.5	0.6
15.0	15.0	C ₁₅ Saturated	—	tr	0.5	0.7	1.0
16.0	16.0	C ₁₆ Saturated	13.8	115.6	15.4	15.0	14.1
16.5	—	—	—	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.8
17.0	17.0	C ₁₇ Saturated	—	0.7	0.6	0.8	0.9
18.0	18.0	C ₁₈ Saturated	2.2	3.7	3.8	3.3	3.9
18.3	17.7	C ₁₈ Monoenoic	5.5	7.7	7.8	7.6	6.9
19.2	17.7	C ₁₈ Dienoic	78.5	68.9	69.0	68.6	68.1
21.6	—	—	—	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.6
22.5	—	—	—	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
25.9	—	—	—	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
29.0	29.0	C ₂₉ Saturated	—	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

the bodied safflower oil and methyl esters were prepared by using dry hydrochloric acid as catalyst¹.

The experimental techniques and analytical methods used in this paper have been described previously¹. The methyl esters of free fatty acids were analyzed and the results are shown in Table 2. The bodied oils were fractionated with acetone, the fractions were analyzed and the physical and chemical characteristics of the soluble fractions are shown in Table 3. The methyl esters by inter-esterification were prepared using sodium methoxide as catalyst from the soluble fractions. They were analyzed in GLC and the results are presented in Table 4. The methyl esters of the samples 6 of Table 1 were distilled at a pressure of 20 μ of Hg pressure. A total of six fractions was obtained. The molecular weights of all the fractions were determined and the results are given in Table 5. The distilled fractions were analyzed by GLC and the results are summarized in Table 6. The IR spectra of the bodied oils and their fractions were taken and the summary of the results are recorded in Table 7.

The methyl esters of the acetone soluble fractions were also analyzed by NMR and the results are

TABLE 2a. COMPOSITION OF FREE FATTY ACIDS FROM BODIED LINSEED OIL

Carbon number on DEGS	Carbon number on Apiezon-L	Tentative identification	Composition Based on DEGS	
			LO	FFA from bodied LO
9.0	9.0	C ₉ Saturated	—	0.8
10.0	10.0	C ₁₀ Saturated	—	0.8
12.0	12.0	C ₁₂ Saturated	—	0.4
13.4	12.5	"	—	0.4
15.6	14.9	"	—	0.7
16.0	16.0	C ₁₆ Saturated	6.9	8.4
17.8	16.5	"	—	0.9
18.0	18.0	C ₁₈ Saturated	3.1	5.2
18.4	17.7	C ₁₈ Monoenoic	21.0	25.9
19.2	17.7	C ₁₈ Dienoic	16.0	18.5
19.9	17.7	C ₁₈ Trienoic	53.0	37.1
21.6	—	—	—	0.3
22.5	19.7	—	—	0.4
23.4	—	—	—	0.4

TABLE 3. PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOLUBLE FRACTIONS

Characteristics	3	4	5	6
Viscosity (stokes)	—	0.65	—	1.0
Acid value	0.0	2.6	4.1	7.2
Peroxide value	tr	tr	tr	tr
Hydroxyl value	4.7	4.8	7.1	12.6
Oxirane value	tr	tr	tr	tr
%Carbonyl groups	0.11	0.21	0.15	0.35
%Molecular weight	—	899	—	897
%Dimeric acids, calc.	—	1.1	—	1.6
%Nonsaponifiable matter, wt. %	—	0.19	0.20	0.23
Presence of α -diketones	+	+	+	+
%Conj. diene acids	11.2	12.1	11.1	23.9
%Trans, calc. as oleate (10.3 μ)	1.1	1.9	2.2	2.7
%Nitrous acid in the bath	1.8	2.3	3.0	3.9

tr = trace.

shown in Table 8. The amount of dimeric acids, A_1 in percentage was found by the following formula as described by Swern *et al.*⁹.

$$A = 66.7 \left(1 - \frac{A_1}{A_n}\right)$$

A_1 = Apparent molecular weight of original triglycerides

A_n = Apparent molecular weight of bodied triglycerides.

Results and Discussion

In this paper studies were made on the acetone-soluble fractions of the bodied oils. The bodying reaction of the safflower oil, as expected, appears to be slower than that of linseed oil. Table 1 shows that even with a flow rate of 1 ml/min. and at a

TABLE 4. BODYING OF SAFFLOWER OIL : FATTY ACID COMPON. OF SOLUBLE FRACTIONS

Carbon number on DEGS	Carbon number on Apiezon-L	Tentative identification	%Composition based on DEGS						
			Safflower oil	1	2	3	4	5	6
7.0	—	—	—	—	—	tr	tr	tr	0.3
8.0	8.0	C ₈ Saturated	—	—	—	—	tr	0.3	0.4
9.0	9.0	C ₉ Saturated	—	—	—	tr	0.6	0.6	0.7
10.0	10.0	C ₁₀ Saturated	—	—	—	tr	tr	tr	tr
11.7	—	—	—	—	—	tr	0.5	0.5	0.6
12.0	12.0	C ₁₂ Saturated	—	—	—	tr	0.7	0.7	0.8
13.5	12.5	—	—	—	—	tr	0.4	0.4	0.4
14.0	14.0	C ₁₄ Saturated	—	—	tr	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.7
15.0	15.0	C ₁₅ Saturated	—	—	tr	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.7
16.0	16.0	C ₁₆ Saturated	13.8	14.5	14.7	15.1	15.2	15.4	15.4
16.5	—	—	—	—	—	tr	tr	tr	tr
17.0	17.0	C ₁₇ Saturated	—	—	—	tr	tr	tr	tr
18.0	18.0	C ₁₈ Saturated	2.2	2.9	2.9	3.6	3.9	3.9	4.0
18.3	17.6	C ₁₈ Monoenoic	5.5	6.2	6.5	7.1	8.0	8.1	8.1
19.2	17.6	C ₁₈ Dienoic	78.5	76.3	76.6	70.0	65.1	65.9	64.7
19.8	—	—	—	—	—	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.8
20.9	—	—	—	—	—	0.7	0.9	0.9	0.9
21.1	—	—	—	—	—	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.6
22.6	—	—	—	—	tr	tr	0.6	0.6	0.7
23.7	—	—	—	—	—	tr	tr	tr	tr

TABLE 5. DISTILLATION OF METHYL ESTER OF SAMPLE 6

(Pressure 20 μ)

Number of fractions	Temp. of distillation (°C)	Amount collected (wt. %)	Molecular weight
I	120—125	27.3	268.8
II	125—130	25.2	286.6
III	130—135	16.7	295.1
IV	135—160	9.3	329.6
V	160—170	7.1	392.2
Residue	—	14.4	591.3

temperature of 320°, the viscosity of the bodied oil increased to only 1.21 stokes. Hence, it was decided to use a polymerization catalyst to help the reaction. A quantity of 0.2% lead oleate (as lead) on oil weight was used. When the rate of flow of oil was held at 12 ml/min., the viscosity of oil, the ARS, increased to 1.01 stokes but without catalyst the viscosity was 0.85 stokes. When the rate of flow of the oil was decreased to 2 ml/min with catalyst, the viscosity increased to 2.4 stokes. Hence, the effect of catalyst is to increase body with the increased in the time of contact.

Table 2 represents the composition of free fatty acids from bodied safflower oil. There are some differences between the composition of free fatty acids (FFA) from linseed (Table 2(a)) and safflower

bodied oils. The acids with carbon numbers 8, 15.6, 19.9 and 23.5 are not present in the safflower bodied oils but some new acids with carbon numbers 11.7, 16.5 and 17.0 are formed. Most of the acids consist of acids already present in the oil, the C₁₇ acid amounts to 1%, the others are less than that. Table 3 shows the physical and chemical characteristics of the soluble fractions. The acid value increases to a maximum of 2.6 with the increase in time of contact when no catalyst was used but it sharply increased to a maximum of 7.2 when the catalyst was used. The hydroxyl value varies from 4.7-4.8 when no catalyst was used but the same increased to between 7.1 and 12.6 when catalyst was used. One remarkable difference from the linseed oil bodying particularly is the formation of peroxides. Only traces were found in ARS but in the case of LO the peroxide values varied from 15.1-39.6. The oxirane group appears also in traces in all the ARS oils. The molecular weight increased slightly and the percent of dimeric acid was 1.6. The amounts to non-saponifiable matter increased to 0.25% which may be due to the decarboxylation of some fatty acids. The amount of conjugated dienes increased to 29.8% with an increase in time of contact and use of catalyst. There is also some formation of nitrous acid in the bath which shows that nitrates are reduced to nitrites indicating the oxidative nature of the bath.*

gradually to 64.7% from 78.5% simultaneously, the increase of all other fatty acids showed that this acid is the most active under the conditions of the reaction.

Tables 5 and 6 show the results of distillation of methyl esters of sample 16. The residue has a molecular weight of 591 which is higher than that of the dimer 560. Theoretically, this indicates the formation of higher molecular weight fatty acids during the reaction. The first fraction contains some lower molecular weight fatty acids together with most of the palmitic acid originally present. The second fraction contains traces of palmitic acid, 28.7% stearic acid, 37.9% oleic acid, 30.4% linoleic acid and traces of higher molecular weight fatty acids. The third and fourth fractions contain mostly dienoic acid. The fifth fraction also contains mostly dienoic acid together with higher molecular weight fatty acids.

Table 7 shows the summary of the IR spectra data. From the relative intensities of the bands at 3010 and 965 cm⁻¹, it is possible to say that *cis*-unsaturation decreased and *trans*-unsaturation increased with the increase in time of contact with use of catalyst. It is also possible to say in the same way that the ratio of -OH/-OOH groups increases with the increase in time of contact and use of catalyst.

TABLE 6. FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF THE DIFFERENT FRACTIONS OF DISTILLED BODIED OILS

Carbon number on DEGS	Carbon number on Apiezon-L	Tentative identification	%Composition based on DEGS				
			I	II	III	IV	V
10.0	10.0	C ₁₀ Saturated	3.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
11.0	11.0	C ₁₁ Saturated	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
11.7	—	—	2.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
12.0	12.0	C ₁₂ Saturated	1.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
13.5	12.5	—	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
14.0	14.0	C ₁₄ Saturated	1.4	tr	0.0	0.0	0.0
16.0	16.0	C ₁₆ Saturated	54.7	1.3	0.5	tr	0.0
16.5	—	—	tr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
17.0	17.0	C ₁₇ Saturated	1.5	1.1	0.9	tr	tr
18.0	18.0	C ₁₈ Saturated	9.8	28.7	5.4	tr	tr
18.3	17.7	C ₁₈ Monoenoic	11.9	37.9	34.6	18.1	4.9
19.2	17.7	C ₁₈ Dienoic	8.1	30.4	58.1	78.8	62.6
21.6	—	—	0.0	tr	0.5	1.8	17.6
22.5	—	—	0.0	0.0	tr	1.0	6.2
29.9	—	—	0.0	0.0	0.0	tr	5.1
30.5	—	—	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6

Table 4 represents the fatty acid composition of the acetone soluble fractions. At 314° and at a rate of 2.5 ml/min., the transformation of the oil is only slight. No new fatty acid was detected in this case. But when the temperature was increased to 320°, even with a higher flow rate, 25 ml/min., a number of new fatty acids are also formed. With the use of catalyst, the amount of these new fatty acids is increased. The dienoic acid content decreased

* Absence of any nitrogen in the bodied oils by sodium fusion shows very little or no nitration of the oil,

Table 8 shows the summary of the NMR analyses of original and soluble fractions of bodied oils. The aromatic proton is absent in all cases except the last one. The aromatic compound may be formed by the disproportionation reaction of the cyclohexene structure formed by the Diels-Alder reaction. The amount of cyclohexene appears also in traces in all cases. The olefinic protons decreased from 3.8 to 3.0-3.4. There is some formation of ether proton in trace quantities only. The amount of diallylic proton decreased from 1.8 to 1.0-1.3. This shows their

TABLE 7. INFRARED DATA OF ORIGINAL AND ACETONE-SOLUBLE OF BODIED SAFFLOWER OILS

Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment	Safflower Oil			
		3	4	5	6
3410-3510	-OOH/-OH	a			
3010	cis-CH = CH-				
2920	C-H Stretching				
2850	"				
1740	C-O Stretching of Ester				
1092	C-O-C of Ether	a			
965	Isolated trans	a			

a = absent; blank spaces indicate absent.

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TABLE 8. PROTON NUMBERS OF METHYL ESTERS OF THE ORIGINAL AND ACETONE-SOLUBLE OF THE BODIED SAFFLOWER OILS

Chemical shift, τ	Type of band	Assignment	Safflower oil	4	5	6
2.7	—	C ₆ H ₅	—	0.0	0.0	tr
4.4	—	—	0.0	tr	tr	tr
4.61	Triplet	-CH = CH-	3.8	3.4	3.6	3.0
6.3	Singlet	CH ₃ -CO-O-	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
6.69	Singlet	-CH ₂ -O-R	0.0	tr	0.0	tr
7.19	Triplet	= CHC-CH ₂ -CH =	1.8	1.3	1.5	1.0
7.91	Apparently doublet	= CH-CH ₂ - and -O-CO-CH ₂	6.7	6.3	6.5	6.0
8.8 to 9.2	Triplet	-CH ₃	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

greater reactivity in the polymerization reaction. However, the decrease in α -methylene protons is very slight. The reaction shows that a number of new fatty acids containing some oxygenated groups are formed. The aromatic, cyclohexene and ether compounds are present only in minor quantities.

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